

Adolescents Anger: Implication for Classroom Instruction

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Abstract

This study examined adolescents' anger, implications for classroom instruction. Adolescent anger is a response to a threat or the perception of a threat against an individual or a group. The types of threat that tend to trigger anger response are broad in scope and include both physical threats and psychological threats or threats to adolescents' are pride or dignity. This is the reason adolescents' anger behaviours differ according to their psychological environment, such behaviours influence their academic achievement. Adolescent anger may be passive or active. Some possible causes of adolescent anger and its effect on adolescents that appear in form of learning difficulties and social adjustment problems were discussed. Strategies and tips to address these problems were provided to help in guiding and improving teaching and learning. This is the reason the researcher recommended that school teacher that has the mastery of the strategies to handle the teaching of students in schools where adolescent anger is exhibited will be properly curbed for effective academic performance of the adolescents. Exhibition of these behaviours in school situation challenges teacher's competence in classroom instruction and lowers academic performance of the students. Violence, aggression and anger metamorphose into other social problem behaviours when not tackled through a concerted effort of the teachers and authorities. The study therefore, x-rays the adolescent anger, with a view to advising teachers on how to manage adolescent anger in classroom situations. Also, provide adequate information on the causes of anger and possible implication to classroom instruction which will tremendously assist teachers in effective classroom control. Proprietors of schools will also benefit as indiscipline resulting from adolescent anger will be reduced in schools. Also counselors will benefit as new methods of addressing adolescent anger problems were highlighted in the recommendations.

Introduction

Adolescent anger and its associated problems have become a life-threatening issue in most primary, secondary and tertiary institutions that need to study its nature and effect to learning has become pertinent to stakeholders in education. (Orji, 2014) Due to the numerous stressors

that exist in our society today, anger has become a common experience for many people, especially adolescents. According to Spielberg as cited in Puskar, Ren, & Bernardo, (2008), there are two aspects of anger namely state anger and trait anger. State anger is an emotional response to a provoking incident, while trait anger tends to occur more frequently in some individuals than others. Trait anger may occur in situations where most people would not respond in the same manner. Anger in adolescents is associated with many problems, including aggression (Csibi, & Csibi, 2011).

According to Novaco as cited in Nancy, (2015), though Anger in adolescents does not always lead to aggression, adolescent anger is often a sign of aggression, disobedient and exhibition of deviant behaviours particularly very intense anger. This type of anger can decrease adolescent's ability to control his or her behaviour. Individual's adolescent express anger differently and for different reasons. Most adolescent think of aggression as the physical expression of their anger, though it is perhaps possible to express anger in nonviolent ways as well. Physical violence, however, is more visible and tends to result in more critical outcomes. The National Center for Education Statistics (2010) study reported that approximately 1.9 million crimes occurred in elementary and secondary schools throughout the nation, meaning about 40 adolescent students per 1,000 were victims of some type. These statistics do not include bullying or cyber-bullying, which are also serious types of aggression. In 2009, 28 percent of students ages 12-18 reported feeling bullied by one or more of their peers (Institute of Educational Sciences, n.d.).

Adolescent anger has also been linked to other serious problems, such as depression, suicide, by cut classes and substance abuse (Daniel, Goldston, Erkanli, Franklin, & Mayfield, 2009).

Adolescent anger manifests in violence tantrum, fighting and even labeling among adolescent students. Its indirect effects appear in learning difficulties and social adjustment problems. Adolescent anger according to (Akinade, 2009) is naturally strong emotion that everyone feels from time to time in response to certain negative experiences. It may be a passing phase of annoyance or full-blown rages. It is an emotional state, that often accompanied by biological changes.

Adolescence is derived from a latin verb 'adolesece' meaning "to grow up". Thus that period of transition from childhood or from dependence on adult direction and protection to self direction and self determination referred to as adolescence. Adolescence is also in this context defined in terms of age span in males and females who are in the period of life from puberty to maturity; boys and girls ranging from 11-20 years old. It is described as the second decade of life that is age 10-21. It is also viewed as a critical period of development, because it is a period of storm and stress. Adolescents are the ones going through the period of physical transition between childhood and adulthood. They are found between two worlds: childhood and adulthood. They are undergoing and internal turmoil. Some of these adolescents are seen to express anger because the agents of socialization (family, church, school, society) have left gaps which they now try to substitute with high incidences of anti-social behaviours. Occasionally when their needs are not

met, they feel neglected by their parents, not being involved in decision making, identity formation these and more can result to anger in the adolescent.

Adolescent anger can be influenced by emotion, neglects. Mild forms of anger may include displeasure, irritation or dislike. When react to criticism, threat or frustration may become angry and this is a healthy responses. Anger may be a secondary response to feeling, sad, lonely or frightened. When anger becomes a full bloom rage our judgment, thinking and cognitive process can become impaired and are more likely to do and say unreasonable and irrational things. (Nordqvist, 2013). Anger causes widespread effects on the body and psychologically can change how each adolescent behaves or performs in the school.

Adolescents

Adolescent are the growing ones in the period in human growth and development that occurs as Rogers in Owuh (2012) sees adolescence as a process rather than a period. Adolescents form their identity not by modeling themselves after other people as older adult do, but by modifying and synthesizing earlier identification. To form an identity, adolescents must ascertain and organize their abilities, needs interests and desires, so as to be expressed in a social context. This Owuh said will influence life in adulthood. The onset of adolescence and the chronological age is between the years from 11 Or 12years to early age of 20 vary from culture to culture, depending on the socio-economic conditions of the country.

Aihie, (2010), added that the adolescent seem to receive with little or no resistance, every change that occurs especially the anger response, which occur naturally. Everything in the world today is dynamic and needs to be so as to determine the positivity and negativity of such changes. The adolescents group is mostly hit in these changes that cut across all facets human life. Adolescent group is marked by the changes in the physical structure and mental ability which makes it a unique period. (Daniel, Goldston, Erkanli, Franklin, & Mayfield, 2009) emphases that adolescence can be a tumultuous period for many youth due to the numerous physical, emotional, and intellectual changes occurring during this time. (Barth, & Wells, 2010) added that many problems can occur when young men and women are adjusting to these changes, one of which is the experience of anger. Though the experience of anger itself is not always negative, in individuals who are not well-equipped to deal with the emotion they may express anger in maladaptive ways, leading to a variety of problems such as aggression, depression, and suicide are few of the problems related to anger. In addition to understanding the impact of anger, it is also important to understand why some adolescents are more likely to experience anger. Social support, bullying, family interactions, personality, and home environment have been identified as contributing factors (either negatively or positively).

Concept of Adolescent Anger:

Adolescent Anger is a person's response to a threat or the perception of a threat against an individual or group (Orji (2014) It can evolve from empathic concern or perception of injustice and is related to genitive factors, such as hostility and cynicism, also an emotion that is often difficult to control because of the intense physiological reactions involved in the fight or flight

responses that trigger anger (Lochman, 2008). This Akinade (2009) had observed that adolescent anger may be passive or active. Passive anger may be exhibited by backstabbing or spreading rumors. Active anger can be shown by yelling or other forms of aggressive or physical outburst.

Causes of Adolescent Anger

There are several causes of anger in different adolescents'. These may include: Identity crisis, demand for autonomy, Failure, Frustration, Harassment/bully, false accusation, Grief-losing a loved one, Injustice, Being –ignored Sicknes Disappointment Withdrawal of some drugs or medicine Mental illness Sloppy services Low academic performance Moodiness Feeling misunderstood, financial problems, Drug abuse, Over learning, Distrust, Jealousy, Conflict over possessions (such as toys, books, land or spouses, Irrational perception of reality (such as emotional reasoning) Your thought pattern about a situation (can cause, worsen or sustain anger) and Spread rumor.

Effects of Adolescent Anger

McElrony (2015) suggest that adolescents with high trait anger are more likely to have interpersonal problems, academic difficulties, and conflict in their jobs. When adolescent students believe they have the necessary resources to deal with difficulties, they are more likely to make wise choices. If, on the other hand, they feel that they cannot face the problem, they may make poor choices. For example Csibi & Csibi (2011), observed that some studies have shown that girls often use avoidance when dealing with stressful situations which causes emotional tension that may have result in adolescent anger. Eventually, that tension must be released in some way, such as aggression towards their peers. This can lead to further interpersonal problems, which may have been the initial cause of the anger.

However, in order for educators and counselors to effectively serve adolescents and identify solutions for preventing these outcomes, it is important for them to be aware of the factors that can contribute to the expression of adolescent anger. Perceived social support, emotion regulation, family environment, and personality are some of the contributing factors (Puskar , et al., 2008; Turblad, Grann, & Lichtenstein, 2010; Sanz, Garcia-Vera, & Magan, 2010). Fortunately, there are several school-based programs that have shown promise in addressing some of the core issues related to adolescent anger. An awareness of the available programs in the field as well as the task of evaluating and researching their effectiveness are crucial steps in addressing the problem of adolescent anger. If schools and mental health professionals can address the problem at an early age, perhaps it will prevent more serious problems during adulthood. Angry behaviours are expected among adolescent, and the occurrence of such behaviours provides important opportunities for socialization and development of self-control (Nancy 2011).

Therefore, to affirm this Powell (2015) added that the display of adolescent anger may be expected in certain situations but not in others. For example aggressive acts during rough housing among friends are likely to be well tolerated whereas similar behaviour may provoke a physical fight outside of a positive social relationship. In other words, adolescent anger is not always bad if

properly managed. It can be a useful and powerful emotion that can motivate adolescent to make positive changes to overcome obstacles and achieve laudable goals. Adolescent anger can be harmful when ignored or expressed in a negative way (Akinade 2009). It can hurt the adolescent and those he interact with. It can lead to arguments, physical abuse, assault, self-harm, resentment fear, anxiety and even murder. Adolescent anger can lead to accidents, example especially on the field of sports or on the road, also can ruin interpersonal relationships at home, in the community, work or school. It can lead to truancy, school absenteeism and poor academic performance amongst the school adolescents.

Ways of Managing Adolescent Anger in the School

Adolescent anger management is a procedure of acquiring the skills to recognize signs that an adolescent is becoming angry and taking actions to deal with the situation in a positive way. Anger is a natural response to being hurt. It is human to be angry. Also, it is human to learn how to control it. Using the following tips below would help school teachers and authorities achieve some goals of adolescent anger management. A good and conducive learning environment should be provided, where adolescent can relax to learn properly, teachers should keep a positive outlook and give a good listening ear to the problems of the adolescent. Try to understand the emotions and the psychological feelings of the adolescents, they should be encouraged to label their feelings, Do not allow the adolescent to sulk in silence. The adolescents who suppress their anger usually experience anxiety or depression and have difficulty in learn. They should avoid being violent, rather mild in expressing or solving their problems.

Implications for the classroom teacher

The class teacher that has no mastery of the strategies to handle the teaching of students in schools where adolescent anger will experience difficulty to properly curbed the adolescent anger for effective academic performance of the adolescents. Exhibition of these behaviours in school situation challenges teacher's competence in classroom instruction and lowers academic performance of the students. Violence, aggression and anger metamorphose into other social problem behaviours when not tackled through a concerted effort of the teachers and authorities. The classroom teacher who have observed adolescent anger in the class should take steps in helping such adolescent overcome their challenges. The class teacher should give clarity to who the adolescent is, and what is his role in the society, teacher should not always at all time spoon-feed the adolescents by way of having their wok planned for them, but involve the adolescents in decision making in the class. The class teacher should not scold them for little misbehaviours, rather the adolescents should be treated in more adult manner and thus encouraged to show adult behaviours in their actions.

The teacher should use democratic practices with frequent explanations of their rules of conduct and expectations. The teacher should not ignore their feelings, rather encourage the adolescents

to express their feelings, label their feelings and it should be treated accordingly. It should be treated calmly and timely because justice delay is justice denied and that can be dangerous to the adolescent, class members, school and society. The teacher should avoid be violent or harsh in solving the problem. Teachers should calmly and politely explore areas that upset the children in the learning process. Teacher should use effective collaborative studies or group work, to reduce adolescent anger behaviours with a team spirit.

Conclusion

Adolescent Anger behaviours are normal experiences in adolescent, but when taken excess they can lead to significant impairment in adolescent's functioning in the classroom situations. Using some of the strategies above such as, learn to relax or calm down or counselling would help teachers and school authorities reduce adolescent anger, thereby improving the quality of education and academic performance of these students. Though stress is a universal experience, it is particularly common in adolescents due to the multitude of changes that occur in their lives. Every adolescent responds differently to stress or a negative event. The way in which he or she responds to a stressor or a provocation of some type could be positive or negative. For instance, some adolescent are able to learn and grow from difficult experiences. They consider their resources and choose a course of action based on how they interpret the situation. Some adolescents have many resources available to them, such as good social support, high self-esteem, a mild temperament, and a comfortable socioeconomic status.

These adolescents are more likely to respond positively to stressful or negative life events. Others, however, may live in a negative home environment, which often translates to a lack of social support or a low socioeconomic status. Furthermore, each adolescent has a different temperament, some of which may be less agreeable than others. These barriers can contribute to adolescents responding in anger to a stress or a provocation. Though some degree of anger is normal, higher levels of anger can be maladaptive, as they are linked to problems like aggression, depression, and suicide.

If mental health professionals would like to assist adolescents in managing their anger effectively, it is important for them to understand what could be causing individual's anger, as well as what the outcomes of that adolescent anger are. Once school teachers, counsellors or community counsellors begin to understand the causes and effects of anger, it will be easier for them to develop and implement a multifaceted approach to the problem. it is important for the class teacher and counsellor to consider the adolescents' culture, as anger is expressed differently and addressed differently depending on a person's background. Counsellors must be in tune with the adolescent so that they can determine if the intervention will be or has been effective. Only then will adolescent anger management interventions be successful in preventing interpersonal, emotional, and legal problems in adulthood.

Recommendations:

1. Adequate counselling on adolescent anger management services should be provided in the school for effective classroom instructions.
2. Teachers should model responsible adolescent anger strategy.
3. Teachers/ counsellors should communicate with parents about the adolescent anger behaviour's in their children.
4. Teachers/ counsellors should teach the adolescents on how to be assertive and not being aggressive in the classroom.
5. Teachers/ counsellors should create a safe emotional climate should during the learning process.
6. Teachers/ counsellors encouraged use of books and stories about adolescent anger to help them understand manage anger in all situations.
7. Teachers should design diplomacy and tack for discipline, also some acceptable strategies of expressing their displeasure.
8. Teachers/ counsellors should teach the adolescents to breathe deeply when they are tense.
9. Teachers should avoid discussing divisive and personal issues, like politics, religion and culture.
10. Teachers should stop using some verbal expressions like, "you are stupid", "shut up", "you are wrong", "Are you mad" rather words like C-A-L-M-D-O-W-N, and R-E-L-A-X can be used for the aggressive adolescent.

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